

RE- INVENTING TEACHER EDUCATION IN CONTEXT OF GLOBALISATION

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Abstract :

Globalisation is a process through which an increasingly free flow of ideas, people, goods, services and capital would lead to the integration of economies and Societies. It is a complex and multi-faceted phenomena which has put an ineradicable impression on all the spheres and levels of life, resulting in growing independence of people across the globe. The Education system is reacting differently to the changes in the world's new economic, political and cultural orders which are changing because of globalisation. It is only through improving the educational status of a society that the multi-faceted development of its people can be ensured. That is why it has become essential for each and every person whether he is a policy maker, reform designer, or educational leader, to understand the impact of globalisation on the process of teaching and learning. Our paper will focus on teacher education in context of globalisation that should respond to the profound global changes taking place in the world today. Teachers training courses should be planned, implemented and assessed thoroughly for the teacher trainees in context of globalisation. Only then our teachers will be globalised in real terms and it is only then we can say that the future generation of our country is in right hands.

Keyword s- *Teacher Education, Globalisation, Higher Education*

Globalisation :

Globalisation is a complex and multi-faceted phenomena which has put an

ineradicable impact on all spheres and levels of life, resulting in growing independence of people across the globe. Globalisation is expected to be a process through which an increasingly free flow of ideas, people, goods, services and capital would lead to the integration of economies and societies. It is characterized by an accelerated flow of trade, capital, and information, as well as mobility of individuals, across geographical borders. It is this construction of time-space compression that has given rise to popular notion of “One-World” “Global Village”. Globalisation has caused a major restructuring of the economy, and the government has reacted in a technocratic way to respond to its necessity. No community is immune from the effects of this revolution. It is changing the very fundamentals of human relations and social life. Today’s massive movements of capital depend on information, communication, and knowledge in global markets. Globalisation has two macro-level consistent effects on our daily lives. First, it simultaneously both integrates and segregates. It integrates world cultures through the global communication networks and less restricted movement of individuals. At the same time it creates a tension between those who are benefiting more and those who may be marginalized by the market values and consumer cultures that are typical to many societies.

How Globalisation is Affecting Higher Education :

The role of the Education Sector lies in nation building. Educational systems are reacting differently to the changes in the world’s new economic, political and cultural orders. As Education is on the concurrent list so the States acceptance becomes essential and this would call for amendments in the Education Acts of the states and universities. The Education sector itself is subjected to globalisation. Globalisation has become an influence in nation’s social reforms as education sectors adjust to the new global environments that are characterized by flexibility, diversity, increased competition and unpredictable change. Understanding the effects of globalisation on teaching and learning has become a necessity for any policy maker, reform designer and educational leader. In global knowledge economies, higher education institutions are more important than ever as mediums for a wide range of cross-border relationships and continuous global flow of people, information,

knowledge, technologies, products and financial capital. Globalisation necessarily changes the conditions of identity formation of the individuals who have multiple identities according to the global markets. Higher education was always more internationally open than most sectors because of its immersion in knowledge. This has created moves to reform higher education in order to produce the necessary technocrats. In global knowledge economies, higher education institutions are more important than ever as mediums for a wide range of cross-border relationships and continuous global flow of people, information, knowledge, technologies, products and financial capital. The higher education in global context has been increasingly transformed into trans-national education. As a result of Globalisation the opportunities in India in the field of Higher Education now, appears to be immense and areas are diverse. With the fast growing Information and communication technology the availability and flow of academic resource materials is providing input to the academicians to compete with their counterparts anywhere in the world. It has been realized that the role of Internet is an interactive medium with potential global reach. It has the capacity to bring knowledge and prosperity to isolated and marginalized individuals and nations. All universities, engineering colleges, medical colleges and other institutions of higher learning, as well as research and development organizations would be networked for distance education programs to improve the quality of education. Various initiatives to promote IT literacy were indicated, including a "Teach the Teachers" program. Education and skills development allow firms and people to take part in globalisation processes. It is important to have a flexible education system in order to adjust to new trading conditions.

Globalisation And teachers :

Education Commission (1964-66) professed, "The destiny of India is now being shaped in her classrooms". Teachers have a pivotal role to play in preparing the young generation to help realize our hopes that the coming century will see a more socially adjust, more tolerant and more peaceful world. The situation of teachers merits the closest attention of all who wish to leave such a world to our children. Teachers have a crucial role to play in preparing the learners not only to face the

future with confidence but to build it with purpose and responsibility. The fundamental challenge before each country is globalisation which impacts lives of all in different ways and meanings. We are witnessing that globalisation is no longer an exclusive domain of the world of economics and the global marketplace. Kofi Aunan (2006), Secretary General of the UN has this to say about globalisation and the challenge before us :

Teaching might not be the most popular profession in the world, but it is undoubtedly the most populated. The World Education Report 1998 investigates how changes in the demographic, economic and technological environment have affected teachers and asks if education policies have successfully drawn benefit from these changes to improve teacher's motivation and performance. The recent economic environment has taken its toll on the teaching profession. It is true that the computer is probably the most children friendly and the most teachers threatening. To realize the vision of globalisation, teacher education should respond to the profound global changes taking place in the world today. The challenges before us are matched by ample opportunities that can help teachers assume their crucial role of educating for global responsibility.

Need to Modify Teacher Education with Respect To Globalisation :

UNESCO's fourth World Education Report(1998), entitled **Teachers and Teaching in a Changing World**, focuses on the role and status of teachers in a world, undergoing rapid transformation in the field of communications and information which obviously has an impact on teachers. It argues convincingly that "what society currently expects from teachers in most countries could be out of proportion to the rewards it is prepared to harmony to teachers and the means typically put at their disposal." It also points to the detrimental impact that some very popular, and seemingly innocent, education policies have had on teachers' status. Teacher education cannot be framed in isolation; it should be conceived in terms of globalisation. Teacher education and school education have a symbiotic relationship and developments in both these sectors mutually reinforce the concerns necessary for Qualitative improvements of the entire spectrum of education including teacher

education as well.

A teacher education curriculum needs to be in consonance with the school education. Teacher education is an important part of higher education system of our country but this course is neglected as compared to the other professional courses. Teaching as considered to be the most respected profession among the female part of the society but still there are many factors which have made lost the importance of this profession. The major factor is the curriculum of the course. There has been many up-gradations done on regular basis by the experts but still it is far behind from the actual scenario of the market which demands more from present teachers of school level. It is the responsibility of teacher education institutions to prepare teachers for the society who work according to the requirement of the society that is the part of world. Their work is to prepare the individuals for globalised world in which the generation has to be absorbed. Although globalisation has also created new opportunities to transform education, this article will try to focus on the reforms that have to be made in teacher education curriculum in accordance of globalisation. Therefore, education must help individuals to perform tasks for which they were not originally trained, to prepare for a non-linear career path, to improve their team skills, to use information independently, to develop their capacity for improvisation as well as their creativity, and finally to lay the basis of complex thinking linked to the harsh realities of practical life. Teacher education will have to make those teachers who are having the required characteristics. Teachers are made responsible to implement the necessary innovations to cope with social and economic changes. They must show capacity to interpret future requirements of work and life and constantly update their knowledge and teaching skills to keep up with rapidly changing global requirements, involving shifts in technology and widening social relations. Teachers are expected to mould students in light of economic trends and challenges, and to pass the skills necessary to create a workforce capable of achieving these. In light of this, teacher education is likely to be highly standardised. The major challenge for most educators is in preparing students for a world that is other than what they take for granted, for a realisation that there is a world outside. Currently, there exists a gap between students' knowledge and skills and those they will need to effectively

navigate an increasingly interconnected world.

Planning and Implimentation of Teacher Education In Context Of Globalisation

It should be holistic and transformative with an overarching goal of attaining a civil society which is committed to a culture of peace technology and can chart the direction of human relations and globalisation.

- Education and training programs for instructional technology should be developed according to innovations which are becoming available in the global marketplace.
- The process and effects of economic and cultural globalisation should be expressed by teacher educators with particular reference to the ways in which the global media (such as television media and internet) are deployed in the construction of knowledge.
- Intel was recognized for the tremendous global success and impact of the Intel Teach Program, which has provided training to more than 7 million teachers all around the world. So this training of Intel Teach Program can be spread to improve teacher effectiveness by organizing this in every session at regular basis.
- For giving knowledge based education the interaction of students with other developed countries can be emphasized.
- Development of humanistic values, creativity, cultural, moral and spiritual dimensions in the teaching-learning process.
- Knowledge of multinational agencies can be embedded in the courses which are working for technological revolution.
- Value education should be inculcated so as to learn importance of empathy, freedom, sharing, honesty, equality, respect that will help for change in global emergence of new types of career.
- English speaking should be emphasized for globalisation as it is the most spoken language in the world and to globalize we require training our students like this only.
- Make the students conversant with issues surrounding cross-border education

and trade to inform the exchange among associations.

- Teacher education should include raising the political consciousness of its students, especially regarding global issues and globalisation.
- We should not give negative examples of others culture as this will change the perception of students.
- The teacher educators of today should produce teachers who can confidently and whole heartedly welcome the changes and blend them in their ways and methods of teaching.
- We should pose good examples of our resources which can reduce the percentage of Brain Drain.
- Mobility of students, administrators, research scholars to other countries for seminars, international conferences would provide them a chance to experience and understand customs and social dynamics.
- Develop the capacities in students to become independent and lifelong learner.
- Personality development should be the part of curriculum for global exposure.
- Technology, especially computers and the internet play an important role in creating and legitimating globalisation. Aware the student about Internet which is a global network, and explains that it provides enormous opportunities for one to explore new communities and perhaps to become part of them.
- Fusion or hybridization of cultures should be emphasized. Training should be given to infuse inter cultural competence.
- Teacher educators should be well trained for globalisation.
- Teacher educator should plan the activities and lectures by using internet sources.
- Teachers should join the various communities on internet like academia.com, so that they can interact with the other educators around the globe. So that they can learn about latest trends in education and share their experiences through blogging, discussion forums and twitter.
- Teacher educators should minimize the use of traditional methods of teaching and Training for effective, democratic, participatory and competent methods should be given to trainees.

- Lecture series for the related topics can be organized by inviting delegates from other countries by the university level.
- Experts from Corporate world can be invited to train for innovative technologies like Educomp, smart classrooms, e-groups.
- They should be trained to celebrate global occasions.
- Teacher educators and trainees teachers can be involved in virtual learning like they can use social networking websites.
- Expose trainees to latest educational technology devices and practical insights.

Assesment for Problems of Implimentation:

- Evaluation tools, techniques and methods are still theoretical and not practical to be at par with the international norms.
- There is lot of subjectivity creep in while implementing and evaluating.
- Online assessment was never done in the curriculum as comparative to other courses.
- The threat is possibility of erosion of national values by imbibing the alien culture.
- The threat is to the Nation's Integrity.
- Regional language is emphasized till higher level so the students are hesitant to speak or use English in daily life.
- Teachers pose bad examples for different cultures.
- Teacher educators are themselves are not technology savvy. They themselves are not able to devote time for ICT.
- Teachers are not ready to use innovative teaching methods.
- Problems of resources are the major factor especially the internet facility.

Conclusion :

As it is known globalisation promises dramatic and rewarding change to the higher education systems of the developed countries. Whereas for the developing and the underdeveloped countries, where the system is facing the scarcity of resource and it threatens the system to come in practice. Developing

countries often have to adjust willingly or unwillingly both to the quickening pulse of international change, and accordingly, reform on several fronts simultaneously. The matter is how to achieve the concrete gains from existing higher system, competing with Global trends without sacrificing national goals of higher education and without abandoning its commitment to Indian tradition and cultural values is a real challenge. We have to shape teacher education in such a way so that it may produce the globally talented students. Teachers are considered as mere functions of the economy at large, as indeed are the students. As globalisation becomes the dominant term for describing and conceptualizing teacher education colleges and schools of education will need to revisit their mission statements and rethink what it means to be part of the global community. Preparing students and faculty for globalisation requires revisiting the idea of both the university and teacher education. There is need for curricular changes in the globalised scenario. We should not imitate but try to made arrangements to meet the demands of globalisation under the constrained conditions too.

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